

Urban arborization in cities of the Brazilian Semiárido: Retrospective analysis and future perspectives

Marcos Antônio Drumond¹, Visêlido Ribeiro de Oliveira¹, Danniely Alves Benício Borges², Iêdo Bezerra Sá¹,
Maria do Carmo Learth Cunha³

¹Researcher Dr. at Embrapa Semiárido, Petrolina-PE

²Teacher Dr. at the University Center of Patos (UNIFIP), Patos-PB

³Teacher Dr. at the Federal University of Campina Grande (UFCG), Patos-PB Campus

ABSTRACT: The study aimed to conduct a case study on the urban arborization of two medium-sized cities located in the semi-arid region of Northeast Brazil (Patos-PB and Petrolina-PE), considering actions already carried out in these cities. Based on qualitative and quantitative phytosociological and geotechnical studies, the predominance of exotic species, such as *Terminalia catappa* and *Ficus benjamina*, was observed in the 1990s and 2000s, respectively. Similar methodological evaluations were implemented in the city of Patos-PB, identifying also *F. benjamina*, among other species. In recent decades, alternatives have been adopted for using native species from the Caatinga biome, characterized by the presence of tree and shrub species with a predominance of deciduous species during the dry period of the year, which can be utilized in arborization. In this sense, with the restructuring of public roads in the two cities, significant advances have been observed in relation to the relative increase in the percentage of local native plants. Thus, with this trend of valuing regional flora in urban centers, public policies to encourage planting and new phytosociological surveys should be prioritized in the next decade or more, to confirm this trend and consider other technical aspects, such as spacing between trees, distances between curb and sidewalk, width of sidewalks, height of power lines, and drastic pruning, among others.

KEYWORDS: Arboriculture, exotic trees, native trees.

INTRODUCTION

The Brazilian semi-arid region is characterized by a typical vegetation type known as Caatinga, which is composed mainly of small-sized woody species with small, deciduous leaves. These plants typically lose their leaves at the beginning of the dry season and are often equipped with thorns, a characteristic commonly found in herbaceous plants, cacti, and bromeliads. Several tree species cited by Drumond et al. (2016) have been incorporated and highlighted in the urban arborization of some cities in the region, such as *Cenostigma pyramidale*, *Handroanthus impetiginosus*, and *Commiphora leptophloeos*. This demystifies the idea that native species would be an obstacle to arborization due to their deciduous nature during the hottest period of the year, as they maintain their foliage for most of the year. Thus, this arborization must be well planned so that native species from the Caatinga biome are used in suitable environments and with available water resources for establishment in field conditions.

In this sense, this problem has been addressed for a long time through the use of evergreen exotic species, such as *Prosopis juliflora* and *Ficus benjamina*. Among the various factors that contribute to improving the quality of life for urban populations, arborization is an important alternative that enhances the environment from both ecological and aesthetic perspectives. Only in recent decades has this practice received due attention and is now part of the planning processes of municipal administrations and even as a government goal.

Larger green city areas can decrease the temperature by avoiding heat islands, which are often observed in large metropolises with intense urbanization, such as Recife and Salvador. A survey conducted by the Brazilian Institute of Geography and Statistics (IBGE, 2022) aimed to identify the most arborized Brazilian capitals. The results showed that Campo Grande was in first place, with 91.4% of households in streets with at least one tree, compared to a national average of 66%. Next are Goiânia (89.6%), Palmas (88.7%), Curitiba (85.2%), Brasília (84.2%), Porto Alegre (76.5%), Belo Horizonte (75.3%), Cuiabá (74.5%), São Paulo (66.2%), Rio de Janeiro (63.9%), Vitória (56.3%), among others, representing the Center-West, North, South, and Southeast regions. In the Northeast region, the capitals are Fortaleza (59.7%), Teresina (57.7%), Natal (55.2%), João Pessoa (53.2%), and Recife (51.1%), among others.

City arborization is not just about planting trees on sidewalks, as plantings must follow specific technical criteria in the formation of green areas in streets, avenues, squares, parks, and public spaces. Thus, to carry out an arborization program, several basic criteria must be considered, including soil conditions, climate, tree size, phenology, the selection of suitable species, quality, and methods of planting seedlings and tree maintenance.

Especially in semi-arid regions, urban vegetation plays a fundamental role and can be considered a crucial factor in mitigating adverse climate impacts and promoting the quality of life for the population. Therefore, the planning of semi-arid cities with urban arborization needs to be carried out correctly and sustainably. Thus, there are conditions for arborization to be effective and produce its real function in these anthropized environments. One of the conditions is the correct choice of species, as the inappropriate use of species in incompatible locations can cause tree falls, problems with power lines, loss of pedestrian space, and other issues.

The Caatinga vegetation does not exhibit the lush greenery of humid tropical forests, and its arid aspect, dominated by cacti and shrubs, suggests low diversification (LEAL et al., 2003). However, according to Giulietti et al. (2004), "the Caatinga contains a great variety of vegetational types, with a high number of species and remnants of well-preserved vegetation, which include a significant number of rare and endemic taxa".

The objective of this chapter is to present the situation of arborization in two medium-sized cities in the Brazilian semi-arid region and offer technical information to minimize the main problems encountered, as well as to report the main benefits of arborization planning in the Brazilian semi-arid region, highlighting management, conflicts, and technologies.

Benefits of Urban Arborization in the Semi-Arid Region of Brazil

The direct and indirect benefits of urban arborization are unquestionable. Directly, we can cite beautification and microclimatological improvement, especially relevant in semi-arid regions. Indirectly, trees provide anti-pollution, acoustic, and visual gains, in addition to benefits for human physical and mental health, which implies socioeconomic benefits. Trees enhance the satisfaction of park and neighborhood users, contributing to increased property values and providing a stimulus to human well-being. Microclimatological and biological improvements are unquestionable, providing a rescue of biodiversity and greater balance between urban ecosystems, in addition to promoting better physical and mental health (CECCHETTO et al., 2014).

Planning of Urban Arborization for the Semi-Arid Region

Before planning, it is necessary to conduct a detailed diagnosis of the current state of urban arborization, as well as the municipal master plan and the Municipal Arborization Law, if applicable.

The classification of species should be carried out according to the indication of use, and can be divided into: a) Species without restrictions: those that are evergreen, fast-growing, easy to propagate, and have pivot roots and a canopy suitable for local conditions, such as wind intensity and construction surroundings, small fruits, and may or may not have intense flowering. b) Species with open canopy: those that have canopies with long or pendulous branches, which may require pruning and formation when strictly necessary. They can be used in wide sidewalk streets with small restrictions. c) Slow-growing species: those with characteristics more suitable for use in larger public areas, which may have more appropriate use when associated with those classified in other indications of use, so as not to depend on rapid growth for shading formation. d) Unknown species: those with little or no information on their behavior, especially in urban areas. e) Species with restrictions on use: those that present undesirable characteristics, such as excessive lateral branching and/or very open canopy, presence of thorns or spines, which release toxic and allergenic substances to humans.

The choice of species should be made according to the specific characteristics of the urban environment to be arborized. This includes considering the width of streets, such as narrow streets (<4 m wide), medium streets (between 4 and 6 m wide), and wide streets or avenues (>6 m wide), as well as parks and other public spaces. In addition, it is essential to consider the origin of species, which can be local native (1), from other national ecosystems (2), or exotic (3), as suggested in Table 1.

According to Milano's (1984) recommendations, the total number of individuals of each species should not exceed 15% of the tree population to avoid compromising the survival of these species when they are susceptible to attack by certain pests and/or diseases.

Environmental conditions - The satisfactory development of plants is dependent on a set of environmental factors and their interactions. Species suitable for each climatic type should be selected, taking into account their genetic origin and adaptability,

which are often overlooked, and can lead to serious future problems, such as branch tip drying, trunk cracks, generalized pest and disease attacks, culminating in many cases with the death of the plant.

The physical and chemical characteristics of soils should be considered. The good development of plants is closely related to the level of fertility and water availability in the soil. This problem is more accentuated in dry regions, where, in addition to high temperatures, soils are generally very sandy and poor in nutrients and organic matter, and with little water availability, requiring some measures to minimize problems until the full establishment of each plant, such as the addition of organic matter, nutrients, and irrigation.

Another important factor that is influenced by trees in the urban environment is atmospheric pollution. Although trees can contribute to mitigating their effects, this is only achievable through the use of species that are tolerant or resistant, depending on the level of pollution. The damage caused by atmospheric pollution is significant and can vary according to the species and pollution levels (MASCARÓ and MASCARÓ, 2010).

The characteristics of trees for arborization, in addition to their aesthetic aspect, should consider: shape and size of the canopy; type of leaves; type of flowers, fruits, and roots; growth rate; climatic adaptability; resistance to pests, diseases, and pollution; avoid species that are hosts of agricultural pests and those that accumulate toxic compounds (SÃO PAULO, 2024).

The planting should be carried out in accordance with four fundamental aspects, namely: site characteristics, seedling characteristics, planting characteristics, and landscape aspects (SÃO PAULO, 2024).

To define the size of the plants, location, and spacing of the pits, the following factors should be considered: the width of streets and sidewalks, the position of electric or telephone wiring, the position and depth of water and sewage networks, and the setback of buildings, as well as the types of local traffic (Table 2).

It is worth highlighting that the adaptation between the size of the tree and the width of the street is of fundamental importance. For streets 4 to 8m wide and sidewalks up to 2m, it is recommended to plant small to medium-sized trees such as *Senna multijuga*, *Bauhinia forficata*, *Senna macranthera*, and *Thevetia peruviana*, *H. impetiginosus*, and for streets over 8m wide and sidewalks over 2m, it is recommended to plant larger species such as *Terminalia catappa*, *Pachira aquatica*, *Cenostigma pluviosum*, *H. chrysotrichus*, *Clitoria fairchildiana*, *Tabebuia aurea*, and *H. impetiginosus*.

For problems with overhead electric wiring, the solution should always be preventive. It is always recommended to use small-sized species, where local characteristics indicate potential future problems, in order to avoid deforming pruning, which has effects contrary to the principles of arborization.

The seedlings to be used should be of good silvicultural and sanitary quality. Produced in suitable containers with a well-formed root system. It is recommended to plant seedlings that are taller than 1.5 m to avoid higher maintenance costs in the final locations.

The planting should be carried out, preferably at the beginning of the local rainy season, to minimize initial irrigation costs and ensure the plants establish quickly. However, if planting is carried out during the dry season, frequent irrigation is recommended until the seedlings are fully established.

Where most of the time the sidewalks are up to 2.00 m wide, trees should be planted at a distance of 25 to 50 cm from the curb. The pits should be at least 40 x 40 x 50 cm, and can be increased depending on the physical-chemical conditions of the soil.

In areas with low-fertility soils, it is recommended to use a 1:1 mixture of good-quality soil and cured manure or organic compost. For chemical fertilization, it is recommended to conduct a soil analysis at multiple locations to determine an appropriate NPK formulation.

Maintenance is necessary regarding the adoption of irrigation practices, fertilization, phytosanitary control, and, eventually, pruning and cleaning.

State of the art of urban arborization in two medium-sized cities in the Brazilian Northeast Semi-arid region

Petrolina-PE

The city of Petrolina is located in the extreme west of the state of Pernambuco, belonging to the micro-region of Sertão do São Francisco. Its geographical coordinates are 09°23'35"S, 40°29'56"W, and its altitude is 377 meters above sea level. The

climate of the municipality is classified as BShw, characterized as hot semi-arid with summer rains. The average annual precipitation varies from 347 to 600 mm, and the average annual temperature is approximately 26°C. The predominant natural vegetation is the hyperxerophilic Caatinga, which is typical of hot and dry environments and is well adapted to rocky soils (JATOBÁ, 2003).

Petrolina is 712 km from the state capital, Recife, PE, and has a territorial extension of 4,561.872 km², of which 244.8 km² corresponds to the urban area and 4,317.072 km² to the rural area. According to IBGE (2025), the estimated population of Petrolina is 418,444 inhabitants.

The expansion of land occupation in the municipality from the 1980s to the present day is remarkable. There was a significant increase in agriculture, especially irrigated agriculture, which has been specializing in fruit exports every year.

The urban area of the municipality experienced significant changes. In the images presented in Figure 1 and Table 3, it is possible to verify these modifications in the dynamics of occupation in the urban geographic space.

Analysis and observations of surveys carried out on urban arborization

One of the first studies on urban arborization in Petrolina was carried out by Lima et al. (1990). Later, others appeared, such as Oliveira et al. (2007), Oliveira et al. (2009), and Alvarez et al. (2009).

In the survey of Petrolina's arborization, Lima et al. (1990) conducted a comprehensive inventory of individuals in the city, utilizing a city map on a scale of 1:10,000. The city was divided into plots of 250 x 250 m to conduct a comprehensive inventory of the arborization of central streets and neighborhoods, including cataloging, mapping, and defining the population of existing trees in urban areas. This information guided the qualitative inventory, which was based on random sampling of 250 m sidewalk plots. Sampling was performed at the 95% probability level, using as a variable, the number of trees found in the plot. Other information, such as planting position, overhead electrical wiring position, and management needs, among others, was collected following the methodology of Milano (1984, 1987) and Biondi (1985).

According to the information presented in Table 4, it is observed that practically all species inventoried by Lima et al. (1990) were exotic, and the presence of 71 tree-shrub species was verified from a total of 8876 trees. Although there was great diversity of species, only 10 species represented 90% of the total number of trees, with *Terminalia catappa* (49.89%) being the most prominent, followed by *Prosopis juliflora* (12.98%). This high percentage of planting a single species, as was the case with *T. catappa*, represented a significant risk to urban arborization in terms of pest and disease occurrence, and consequently, the decimation of the species. According to Grey and Deneke (1978), as cited by Milano (1987), the recommended species distribution should be between 10% and 15% of the street plantings in a city, considering both aesthetic and phytosanitary aspects.

Of the twenty neighborhoods evaluated (Table 5), it was observed that the distribution of species and individuals was more intense in the central region. However, on the main streets, where commercial stores predominated, the presence of trees diminished. It was found that the highest rate of trees per kilometer of sidewalk was in the neighborhoods Vila Mocê/Jardim Paulo Afonso (37.13), Km 2 (37.04), and Centro (32.79). Estimating the use of regular spacing of 15 meters between trees, the number of trees/km of sidewalk was 67. However, comparing this value with those obtained in the Table, it was 13/Km of sidewalk (LIMA et al., 1990).

Regarding the qualitative conditions of the trees, 1066 trees, corresponding to 36 species and accounting for 12% of the total number of inventoried trees, were evaluated. In general, the characteristics evaluated in the trees, such as vigor, resistance to pests and diseases, and mechanical injury, indicated that 63% of the trees, regardless of the species, were good, 33% satisfactory, 3% poor, and 1% dead (LIMA et al., 1990).

As most of the analyzed trees had their heights conditioned to the height of the street electrical wiring, and were often subjected to lowering pruning, this condition made analysis impossible. The average values for circumference at breast height (CBH), crown diameter (CD), and height of the first bifurcation (Hb) of the main inventoried species can be seen in Table 6 (LIMA et al., 1990).

The evaluation of the dimensions of the crowns of some species did not accurately represent their original shape, as they underwent periodic conformation pruning. This practice should be well evaluated and planned, as the city of Petrolina-PE, located in the semi-arid region of Northeast Brazil with high isolation, directly implies an increase in temperature in the urban area. Regarding the height of the first bifurcation, the sampled trees had an average height of 2.21m from the ground, which is slightly

higher than the recommended height by Miranda (1970). Thus, most of the species presented in Table 6 were below the recommended bifurcation height.

Still, according to Table 6, information is presented on the planting system, specifically pertaining to the items curb, distance from construction, wiring, spacing, and free area. It was found that the average distance of trees to the curb was 0.39m and 1.56m to the buildings. According to Santiago (1983), these values should be between 0.30 and 0.40m in street arborization. Regarding electrical wiring, it was observed that 436 trees (41%) were planted under wiring, at an average distance of 0.29m from its projection and that most of the planted species were large as was the case of *T. catappa* that could be planted under wiring in the conditions, due to the conformation of its crown, whose primary branches were thrown in layers, facilitating the pruning of conformation and conduction.

Regarding the spacing adopted, it varied according to the species planted and was below that recommended by Souza (1969) and Santiago (1983). For small trees, distances of 5 to 7 meters are typically used, while for large trees, distances of 10 to 15 meters are recommended. In the inventory carried out, spacings of less than 10m were observed for large species (*T. catappa*, *Prosopis juliflora*, and *Mangifera indica*).

Regarding the free area of sidewalk paving where the trees were planted, the average free space found was 0.57 m². Among the species and the position in relation to the sidewalk, there was variation in the size of the growth area of the plants. However, in the central flower beds, it was observed that the average area for *Spathodea campanulata* and *Eucalyptus* sp. was greater than 1 m².

New surveys on the urban arborization were reported by Oliveira et al. (2007). In this work, 22 green spaces were selected in the urban center of the city of Petrolina. According to the study, of the 36 species found, 66% corresponded to exotic species, 21% were native to other biomes, and only 13% were native to the Caatinga Biome. Twenty-eight botanical families were also identified, with the Leguminosae family presenting the highest percentage (20%).

In another survey conducted by Oliveira et al. (2009), the central area of the city of Petrolina, PE, encompassing 387.6 Km² and comprising a total of 87 streets and 13 squares, was inventoried. The central map of the city was used for georeferencing, mapping, and identification of native and exotic tree individuals, as well as for collecting information on plant height, crown size, type of pruning, phytosanitary status, associated damage, and the presence of an electrical network.

According to the results, 3130 individual trees were surveyed (Table 7), distributed in 18 families, 43 genera, and 53 species. In relation to the total number of individuals, it was observed that 90.22% were exotic and 9.78% native to Brazilian biodiversity. The most representative families were Fabaceae (35.15%), Arecaceae (14.80%), and Anacardiaceae (9.26%).

Still, according to Oliveira et al. (2009), the ten species that presented the highest abundance were *Ficus benjamina*, *Azadirachta indica*, *Moquilia tomentosa*, *T. catappa*, *P. juliflora*, *Cassia siamea*, *Phoenix dactylifera*, *Leucena leucocephala*, with 41.21%, 9.17%, 6.39%, 5%, 4.15%, 4.15%, 3.8%, 1.66%, 1.31% and 1.12%, respectively. In the comparison between the two surveys, Lima et al. 1990 and Oliveira et al. (2009), *F. benjamina* (OLIVEIRA et al., 2009) prevailed in abundance when compared to *T. catappa* (LIMA et al., 1990).

According to Oliveira et al. (2009), a Pernambuco state law provides for the planting of 50% of species from the Biome. This percentage, as defined by law, serves as an indication to support municipalities in their efforts to plant species in street arborization.

According to a study by Oliveira et al. (2009), 58.29% of the trees exhibited drastic pruning, 39.28% were under electrical wiring, and 2.85% and 3.96% were affected by diseases and pests, respectively.

Based on the survey of the arborization of the central streets of Petrolina-PE, conducted by Oliveira et al. (2009), it was possible to use geotechnology to spatialize the individuals sampled in the previous study (ALVAREZ et al., 2009). The trees were georeferenced using the Global Positioning System (GPS). The referred information was stored in a Geographic Information System (GIS) and integrated with cartographic base information, contemplating streets, blocks, squares, and buildings for the presentation of spatial data. According to the results, 2720 individuals were spatialized, representing 15 families, 37 genera, and 43 species. The most representative families in relation to the number of species were Fabaceae (38.10%), Arecaceae (14.29%), and Bignoniaceae (9.52%), and the three most representative species were *F. benjamina* (44.89%), *A. indica* (9.78%), and *L. tomentosa* (7.28%). Thus, the use of geotechnologies represented the effectiveness of fundamental technology for interdisciplinary studies aiming at the

integration of "layers" in the program, with the objective of studying environmental and urban phenomena to support conservation, management, and reintegration programs in the center of Petrolina (ALVAREZ et al., 2009).

In Figure 2, the main local native species used in the urban arborization of Petrolina-PE are illustrated, with emphasis on *T. aurea* in two phenophases. In Figure 3, the native species from other ecosystems in Brazil are shown, and in Figure 4, the exotic species that predominated until 2009 are depicted.

Patos-PB

The city of Patos-PB, located in the Vale do Rio Espinharas, occupies an area of 512.791 km², of which 5.12 km² corresponds to the urban area. According to IBGE (2025), the estimated population of Patos-PB is 108,104 inhabitants. The city is 307 km from the capital, João Pessoa. The predominant vegetation is Caatinga, and the climate in Patos is characterized as semiarid, with average annual temperatures of approximately 27.5 °C. The region experiences low levels of precipitation throughout the year, with an average annual precipitation of approximately 390 mm, classified as BSh in the Köppen-Geiger climate classification. The urban area of the municipality of Patos comprises 23 neighborhoods (IBGE, 2020). For the realization of this work, six neighborhoods were selected as the study area: Brasília, Centro, Maternidade, Novo Horizonte, Jatobá, and Liberdade.

Qualitative evaluation of street arborization in Patos, Paraíba

The inventory method used for the survey of arborization was that of sampling with probability proportional to size, proposed by Michi and Couto (1996), which involves counting the number of trees per kilometer of sidewalk.

The identification of tree species and palm trees was performed, and their popular names, scientific names, and families were assigned to them. For the confirmation of taxonomy, botanical material was collected, whenever possible, with the presence of flowers, for the preparation of exsiccates for later identification and deposition in the Herbarium of the Center for Health and Rural Technology/Federal University of Campina Grande, Patos Campus, as well as a photographic record of the individuals. The species were classified according to their origin, into native and exotic (BORGES, 2019).

Regarding the floristic composition, 2,758 individuals of 38 species were quantified during the sampling of the six neighborhoods, distributed across 36 genera and 15 botanical families (Table 8). The following plant types were observed: trees, shrubs, and palm trees.

The presence of 15 botanical families was verified in the arborization of Patos-PB: Anacardiaceae, Apocynaceae, Areaceae, Bignoniaceae, Boraginaceae, Combretaceae, Euphorbiaceae, Fabaceae, Malvaceae, Meliaceae, Moraceae, Moringaceae, Myrtaceae, Rhamnaceae, and Rutaceae.

The family that presented the greatest wealth of species was the Fabaceae family, with 10 species, represented by *Delonix regia*, *Senna siamea*, *Cassia fistula*, *Bauhinia monandra*, *Tamarindus indica*, *Albizia lebeckk*, *Erythrina velutina*, *Adenanthera pavonina*, *P. juliflora*, and *Pithecellobium dulce* (Figure 5), while Anacardiaceae was the second family with the highest number of species represented by *Spondias dulcis*, *Astronium urundeuva*, *Anacardium occidentale*, and *M. indica*.

The Areaceae family was represented by the five palm trees: *Veitchia merrillii*, *Dypsis decaryi*, *Phoenix roebelenii*, *Roystonea regia*, and *Dypsis lutescens* (Figure 6), while for the Bignoniaceae family, four species were found: *H. impetiginosus*, *Tecoma stans*, *H. chrysotrichus*, and *T. aurea*.

The other families were represented by one or two species. The representative of the Boraginaceae family was the species *Cordia africana*. For the Combretaceae family, the representative species is *T. catappa*, an exotic tree commonly used in urban landscaping, with five genera found in Brazil. The Euphorbiaceae family was represented by *Jatropha mollissima* and *Cnidoscolus quercifolius*. They stand out for having many economically important families. The Malvaceae family has 787 species in Brazil. It features ornamental plants, such as poppies. The Meliaceae family was represented by *A. indica*, an exotic species widely used in urban arborization, in the Semi-arid region for its shade provided by the wide crown of dense foliage.

The species *C. africana*, *T. catappa*, *C. quercifolius*, *J. mollissima*, *P. aquatica*, and *A. indica* are illustrated in Figure 7.

The Moringaceae family was represented *Moringa oleifera*, which is a fast-growing species, indicated for diversification of culture, in the coastal tablelands and coastal lowlands of Northeast Brazil (RANGEL, 1999), and can be used in arborization in cities in the semi-arid region of Brazil. For the Moraceae family, it was represented by *F. benjamina*, a species with ornamental value, widely used in urban arborization in the 1990s, but recently forgotten for this purpose due to the aggressiveness of its root

system, which destroys sidewalks, walls, and houses. The Myrtaceae family was represented by azeitona (*Syzygium cumini*) and eucalipto (*Eucalyptus globulus*), whose genus is the most important in Brazil, due to its great potential for wood biomass production. *Sarcophagus joazeiro*, native to the Brazilian Semi-arid, was the only representative species of the Rhamnaceae family. For the Rutaceae family, the only species cataloged was the lemon tree, *Citrus limonum*.

The species *M. oleifera*, *F. benjamina*, *E. globulus*, *S. cumini*, *S. joazeiro*, and *C. limonum* are illustrated in Figure 8.

Five species were represented in all neighborhoods: *C. africana*, *A. indica*, *P. juliflora*, *S. siamea*, and *F. benjamina*, all of which are exotic to Brazilian biodiversity.

The neighborhood with the greatest wealth of species was Maternidade, with 22 species, and greater abundance with 737 individuals. The 737 individuals were distributed in 11 botanical families, 22 genera, and 22 species, with the Fabaceae family being the one with the highest number of species (06), *Adenanthera pavonina*; *Albizia lebeek*; *Delonix regia*; *Pithecellobium dulce*; *P. juliflora*; *S. siamea*, which added up to 27.27% of the sampled species.

For the Brasília neighborhood, the 180 individuals cataloged were distributed in 10 botanical families, 17 genera, and 17 species. The richest family in species was Fabaceae (05), *A. pavonina*; *A. lebeek*; *P. dulce*; *P. juliflora* and *S. siamea*, adding up to 29.41% of the sampled species, while in the Novo Horizonte neighborhood, 419 individuals were counted, distributed in 07 botanical families, 10 genera and 10 species, with the Fabaceae family represented by the three species (30%), *D. regia*, *P. juliflora* and *S. siamea*, the richest.

Eleven botanical families were sampled in the Liberdade neighborhood, and the 571 individuals surveyed were distributed in 19 genera and 19 species. Fabaceae was represented by seven species (36.8%): *A. pavonina*, *A. lebeek*, *Erythrina velutina*, *D. regia*, *P. juliflora*, *S. siamea*, *P. dulce*.

In the Center, the neighborhood with the lowest abundance, the 260 individuals were distributed in 08 botanical families, 16 genera, and 17 species, with the greatest richness of the Fabaceae family (07), *A. pavonina*, *A. lebeek*, *Cassia fistula*, *D. regia*, *P. juliflora*, *S. siamea*, and *P. Dulce*.

For the floristic survey carried out in the Jatobá neighborhood, the 591 individuals were distributed in 09 botanical families, 16 genera, and 16 species, with eight of these, from the Fabaceae family (50%), represented by *A. pavonina*, *A. lebeek*, *Cassia fistula*, *B. monandra*, *P. juliflora*, *S. siamea*, and *Tamarindus indica*.

Of the total of 38 species surveyed, 28 are exotic species (73.68%) and 10 native species from Brazil (26.31%). In a survey carried out in the Center of the City of São Joaquim, SC, of the 35 species found, 25 species were exotic (71.43%) and 10 native (SOUZA et al., 2014), while in the city of Piracicaba/SP, the total of exotics was 60.3% (ISERNHAGEN et al., 2009).

The analysis of the presence of exotic and native species in each neighborhood, separately, showed 98.9% exotics in the Brasília neighborhood, with only 1.1% of natives. The predominant exotic species is *A. indica* (49%), followed by 15% of *P. juliflora*. The native species found were *P. aquatica* and *H. impetiginosus*. The same scenario is presented in the Maternidade neighborhood, where 99% of the species are exotic, and 1% are native, with a predominance of *A. indica* (84%) and *F. benjamina* (5%). The native species are represented by *A. occidentale*, *H. impetiginosus*; *J. mollissima*, and *T. aurea*.

In the Novo Horizonte neighborhood, 99.5% of street trees are exotic, and only 0.5% are native. Almost all exotics are represented by *A. indica* (93%), followed by *C. africana* (5%), while the native species are *H. impetiginosus* and *T. aurea*. For the Liberdade neighborhood, 97% of the residents are foreign, where *A. Indica* (84%) and *F. benjamina* (5%) predominate. The native species were represented by *M. urundeuva*, *T. peruviana*; *H. impetiginosus*, *C. quercifolius*, *Erythrina velutina*, and *T. aurea*.

The city center presented the lowest percentage of exotics, although still very high, with 88% (55% of *A. indica*). The 12% natives were classified as *H. chrysotrichus*; *H. impetiginosus*, and *T. aurea*. Finally, the Jatobá neighborhood had 99% exotic and only 1% native species on its streets, with a predominance of *A. indica*. Additionally, *S. joazeiro* and *B. monandra* appeared as native species.

All neighborhoods had a high percentage of exotic species in their composition, above 95%, except for the Center, which had a value below 90%. The result obtained was due to the Center having undergone a recent reforestation process, with native species being planted in the arborization through projects developed by the City Hall of Patos.

A large number of exotic species are present in the Brazilian scenario of urban arborization (SOUZA et al., 2014). Since colonial times, there has been a prevalence of using species from other regions, as immigrants brought cultivated plants from their places of origin, ranging from medicinal plants to ornamental plants (HEIDEN et al., 2006).

Great resistance to the use of native species permeates the entire history and evolution of urban landscaping in Brazil. However, in the 20s, the architect and urbanist Burle Marx emerged, representing a milestone in world and Brazilian landscaping, for presenting a line of conception of its own, using native species, thus extinguishing the use of exotic species, valuing Brazilian flora, where in the 20th century, national landscape architecture was consolidated (MACEDO, 1999).

Final considerations

Petrolina, like many cities in the interior of Northeast Brazil, still faces technical limitations in developing urban green areas.

The current conflicts related to urban arborization are linked to the difficulties of managing plantations, which should be based on prior planning and consideration. This enables decision-making aligned with the standards of large urban centers, with emphasis on the use of native species.

Previously, municipalities distributed seedlings to communities, which resulted in the predominance of certain species, such as *Prosopis juliflora*, *Terminalia catappa*, *Ficus benjamina*, and *Azadirachta indica*. However, a new format of urban arborization is being made possible through the Urban Arborization Master Plan Bill for Petrolina-PE, approved by the City Council. This plan aims to improve the management of urban green areas, prioritizing native species of the Caatinga biome, as mandated by State Law No. 12,857/2005, which requires the incorporation of 50% native species in the city's arborization.

The greatest difficulty in the development, management, and handling of urban arborization is associated with the lack of environmental awareness among public managers, institutions, and the general public. To minimize conflicts, it is necessary to adapt urban infrastructures, such as electrical, telephone, water, and sewage networks, while preserving the integrity of trees and reducing vandalism.

The expansion of green areas and the implementation of new public policies require collective environmental training, involving not only the direct managers but also public managers, institutions, and communities. Based on the information presented, it is expected to provide important subsidies for the training of public agents committed to the necessary changes, valuing urban arborization and minimizing existing conflicts.

We thank the Project Director of AMMA - 2021 (Municipal Environmental Agency of Petrolina), Victor Flores, for his collaboration in this topic.

REFERENCES

1. ALVAREZ, I. A.; OLIVEIRA, U. R.; CARVALHO, C. L.; TAURA, T. A. Uso de geotecnologias para subsidiar planos de ação da arborização viária de centro de Petrolina-PE. In: CONGRESSO BRASILEIRO DE ARBORIZAÇÃO URBANA, 13., 2009, Rio Branco. Diversidade na floresta e na cidade: coletânea de trabalhos. Rio Branco: Sociedade Brasileira de Arborização Urbana, 2009. 1 CD-ROM.
2. BIONDI, D. Diagnóstico da arborização de ruas da cidade do Recife-PE. 1985. 188 f. Dissertação (Mestrado em Engenharia Florestal) - Universidade Federal do Paraná. Curitiba.
3. BORGES, D. A. B. Arborização na cidade de Patos/PB: diagnóstico, benefícios térmicos da vegetação urbana e potencialidades paisagísticas de espécies nativas da Caatinga. 2019. 181 f. Tese (Doutorado em Desenvolvimento e Meio Ambiente) - Universidade Federal da Paraíba. João Pessoa.
4. CECCHETTO, C. T.; CHRISTMANN, S. S.; OLIVEIRA, T. D. de. Arborização Urbana: Importância e benefícios no planejamento ambiental das cidades. In: SEMINÁRIO INTERNACIONAL DE EDUCAÇÃO NO MERCOSUL, 16., 2014, Cruz Alta. Anais... Cruz Alta: UNICRUZ, 2014. Disponível em: <https://www2.ufrb.edu.br/petmataatlantica/images/PDFs/ARTIGO-ARBORIZACAO-URBANA-IMPORTANCIA-E-BENEFICIOS-NO-PLANEJAMENTO-AMBIENTAL-DAS-CIDADES-1.PDF>. Acesso em: 10 jun. 2021
5. DRUMOND, M. A.; KIILL, L. H. P.; RIBASKI, J.; AIDAR, S. de T. Caracterização e usos das espécies da Caatinga: subsídio para programas de restauração florestal na Unidades de Conservação da Caatinga (UCCAs). Petrolina: Embrapa Semiárido, 2016. 37 p. il.
6. GIULIETTI, A. M.; et al. Diagnóstico da vegetação nativa do Bioma Caatinga, In: SILVA, J. M. C.; TABARELLI, M.; FONSECA, M. F.; LINS, L. V. (Org.). Biodiversidade da Caatinga: áreas e ações prioritárias. Brasília, DF: Ministério do Meio Ambiente: Universidade Federal de Pernambuco, 2004. p. 47-78.

7. HEIDEN, G.; BARBIERI, R. L.; STUMPF, E. R. T. Considerações sobre o uso de plantas ornamentais nativas. Revista Brasileira de Horticultura Ornamental, v. 12, n. 1, p. 2-7, 2006.
8. IBGE 2022. <http://cidades.ibge.gov.br/informações_geoambientais> Acesso em: 10 de junho de 2021.
9. IBGE Patos. 2020. Disponível em: <<https://cidades.ibge.gov.br/brasil/pb/patos/panorama>>. Acesso em: 10 de junho de 2021.
10. IBGE 2025. População estimada de Patos: Disponível em:<<https://www.ibge.gov.br/cidades-e-estados/pb/patos.html>> Acesso em 27 de junho de 2025
11. IBGE 2025. População estimada de Petrolina: Disponível em: <<https://www.ibge.gov.br/cidades-e-estados/pe/petrolina.html>> Acesso em 27 de junho de 2025
12. ISERNHAGEN, I.; LE BOURLEGAT, J. M. G.; CARBONI, M. Trazendo a riqueza arbórea regional para dentro das cidades: possibilidades, limitações e benefícios. Revista da Sociedade Brasileira de Arborização Urbana, v. 4, n. 2, p. 117-138. 2009.
13. JATOBÁ, L. Vegetação. In: ANDRADE, M. C de (Coord). Atlas escolar de Pernambuco: espaço geo-histórico e cultural. 2. ed. amp. e atual. João Pessoa: Grafset, 2003.
14. LEAL, I.; TABARELLI, M.; SILVA, J. Ecologia e conservação da Caatinga. Recife: Ed. Universitária da UFPE, 822 p. 2003.
15. LIMA, P. C. F.; OLIVEIRA, V. R. de; NASCIMENTO, C. E. de S.; TORRES, S. B. Diagnóstico da arborização de ruas de Petrolina-PE. In: ENCONTRO NACIONAL SOBRE ARBORIZAÇÃO URBANA, 3.,1990, Curitiba. Anais... Curitiba: FUPEF, 1990. p. 41-53.
16. MACEDO, S. S. Quadro do paisagismo no Brasil. São Paulo: USP, 1999. 144. p.
17. MAP BIOMAS BRASIL. 2020. Página inicial. Disponível em: <https://mapbiomas.org/>. Acesso em: 15 jun. 2021.
18. MASCARÓ, L.; MASCARÓ, J. L. Vegetação urbana. 3. ed. Porto Alegre: Masquatro, 2010. 212 p.
19. MICHI, S. M. P.; COUTO, H. T. Z. Estudo de dois métodos de amostragem de árvores de rua na cidade de Piracicaba – SP. In: CURSO EM TREINAMENTO SOBRE PODA EM ESPÉCIES ARBÓREAS FLORESTAIS E DE ARBORIZAÇÃO URBANA, 1., 1996, Piracicaba. Curso... IPEF: USP, 1996. p. 11-17.
20. MILANO, M. S. Avaliação e análise da arborização de ruas de Curitiba, PR. 1984, 130 f. Dissertação (Mestrado em Ciências Florestais) – Universidade Federal do Paraná, Curitiba.
21. MILANO, M. S. O planejamento e replanejamento de arborização de ruas. In: ENCONTRO NACIONAL SOBRE ARBORIZAÇÃO URBANA, 2, 1987. Maringá, Anais... Maringá, Prefeitura Municipal de Maringá,1987. p. 1-8.
22. MIRANDA, M. A. de L. Arborização de vias públicas. Campinas: IAC, 1970. 49 p. (IAC. Boletim Técnico, 64).
23. OLIVEIRA, U. R.; SILVA, M. P. da; VASCONCELOS, V. A. F. de; ALVAREZ, I. A. Arborização urbana do centro de Petrolina-PE. In: CONGRESSO BRASILEIRO DE ARBORIZAÇÃO URBANA, 13, 2009, Rio Branco. Diversidade na floresta e na cidade: coletânea de trabalhos. Rio Branco: Sociedade Brasileira de Arborização Urbana, 2009. 1 CD-ROM.
24. OLIVEIRA, V. M. do N.; PARANHOS, L. G.; ALVAREZ, I. A. Levantamento qualitativo de espécies vegetais nos espaços verdes urbanos do centro de Petrolina, PE. In: JORNADA DE INICIAÇÃO CIENTÍFICA DA EMBRAPA SEMI-ÁRIDO, 2., 2007, Petrolina. Anais... Petrolina: Embrapa Semi-Árido, 2007. p. 27-31. (Embrapa Semi-Árido. Documentos 205).
25. RANGEL. M. S. A. *Moringa oleifera*: uma planta de uso múltiplo. Aracaju: Embrapa Tabuleiros Costeiros. 1999. 41 p. (EMBRAPA-CPATC. Circular técnica, 9).
26. SANTIAGO, A. da C. Arborização das cidades. Campinas, SP. CATI, 1983. 19 p. (CATI, Boletim Técnico, 90).
27. SÃO PAULO (Município). Secretaria Municipal do Verde e do Meio Ambiente. Manual Técnico de Arborização Urbana. 3. ed. São Paulo: PMSP, 2024.
28. SOUZA, D. N. N.; CAMACHO, R. G. V.; MELO, J. I. M. de; ROCHA, L. N. G. da; SILVA, N. F. Estudo fenológico de espécies arbóreas nativas em uma unidade de conservação de caatinga no Estado do Rio Grande do Norte, Brasil. Biotemas, v. 27, n. 2, p. 31-42. 2014.
29. SOUZA, H. M. de. Arborização de ruas. O Agrônomo, v. 21, n. 5/12, p. 106-134, 1969.

Table 1. Species indicated for urban arborization, classified as: local native (1), from other national ecosystems (2), exotic (3). Indicated for: narrow streets (RE), medium and wide streets/avenues (RM/RA), parks, squares, and public places (PP), in cities of the Brazilian Semi-arid, especially Petrolina-PE.

Tree and Shrub Species	O	RE	RA	PP
Algaroba - <i>Prosopis juliflora</i> (SW) DC.	3		X	X
Algodão-da-praia - <i>Talipariti pernambucense</i> (Arruda) Bovini	2	X	X	X
Angico - <i>Anadenanthera colubrina</i> Benth.	1		X	X
Angico-de-bezerro - <i>Pityrocarpa moniliformis</i> (Benth.) Luck. & R.W.Jobs.	1			X
Aroeira - <i>Astronium urundeuva</i> (M.Allemão) Engl.	1			X
Azeitona - <i>Syzygium cumini</i> (L.) Skeels	3		X	X
Baraúna - <i>Schinopsis brasiliensis</i> Engl.	1			X
Canafistula - <i>Senna multijuga</i> (Rich.) H. S. Irwin & Barneby	2	X		
Canafistula de besouro - <i>Senna spectabilis</i> (Collad.) Irwin et Barn.	2	X		
Canafistula verdadeira - <i>Cassia siamea</i> Lam.	2		X	
Carnaúba - <i>Copernicia prunifera</i> (Miller) H. E. Moore	1		X	X
Castanhola - <i>Terminalia catappa</i> L.	3		X	X
Catingueira - <i>Cenostigma pyramidale</i> (Tul.) Gagnon & G.P.Lewis	1	X	X	X
Catingueirinha - <i>Cenostigma microphyllum</i> (Mart. ex G.Don) G.& G.P.L.	1	X		
Chapéu-de-Napoleão - <i>Thevetia peruviana</i> (Pers.) Schum.	3	X		
Cola - <i>Cordia africana</i> Lam.	3			X
Craibeira - <i>Tabebuia aurea</i> (Silva Manso) Benth. & Hook. f ex S. Moore	1		X	X
Ficus-benjamim - <i>Ficus-benjamina</i> L.	3			X
Ipê branco - <i>Tabebuia roseoalba</i> (Ridl.) Sand.	2	X	X	
Ipê-amarelo - <i>Handroanthus chrysotrichus</i> (Mart. ex DC.) Mattos	2		X	
Ipê-de-jardim - <i>Tecoma stans</i> (L.) Kunth	2	X		
Jambo - <i>Syzygium malaccense</i> L. Merr. & L. M. perry	3		X	X
Jatobá - <i>Hymenaea courbaril</i> L.	2			X
Joazeiro - <i>Sarcomphalus joazeiro</i> (Mart.) Hauenschild	1			X
Licuri - <i>Syagrus coronata</i> (Mart.) Becc.	1		X	X
Manduirana - <i>Senna macranthera</i> (Collad.) Irwin et Barn.	2	X		
Manga - <i>Mangifera indica</i> L.	3			X
Marizeiro - <i>Geoffroea spinosa</i> Jacq.	2			X
Mata-Fome - <i>Pithecellobium dulce</i> (Roxb.) Benth.	3		X	X
Mororó - <i>Bauhinia cheilantha</i> (Bong.) Steud.	1	X		
Munguba - <i>Pachira aquática</i> Aubl.	2		X	X
Nim - <i>Azadirachta indica</i> A. Juss	3		X	X
Oiti - <i>Moquilea tomentosa</i> Benth.	2		X	
Paineira - <i>Ceiba speciosa</i> (A.St.-Hil.) Ravenna	2			X
Palmeira-imperial - <i>Roystonea oleracea</i> (Jacq.) O. F. Cook	3			X
Palmeira-veitchia - <i>Veitchia merrillii</i> (Becc) H. E. Moore.	3		X	
Pata-de-vaca - <i>Bauhinia forficata</i> Link	2	X		X
Pau-Brasil - <i>Paubrasilia echinata</i> (Lam.) Gagnon, H.C.Lima & G.P.Lewis	2			X
Pau-d'arco - <i>Handroanthus impetiginosus</i> (Mart. ex DC.)	1		X	X
Pau-ferro - <i>Libidibia ferrea</i> (Mart. ex Tul.) L.P.Queiroz.	2	X		
Sete-cascas - <i>Handroanthus spongiosus</i> (Rizzini) S.Grose	1	X		

Sibipiruna - <i>Cenostigma pluviosum</i> var. <i>peltophoroides</i> (Benth.) Ggnon & G.P.Lewis	2	X
Tamareira - <i>Phoenix dactylifera</i> L.	3	X
Tamarindo - <i>Tamarindus indica</i> L.	3	X
Tamboril - <i>Enterolobium contortisiliquum</i> (Vell.) Morong	2	X
Turco - <i>Parkinsonia aculeata</i> L.	3	X
Umburana-de-cheiro - <i>Amburana cearensis</i> (Allemão) S.C. Sm.	1	X
Umbuzeiro - <i>Spondias tuberosa</i> Arruda	1	X

O - Origin, RE - Narrow Streets, RA - Medium and Wide Streets/Avenues, PP - Parks and Squares

Adapted from Lima et al. (1990) ^{1 2}.

Table 2. Recommended Tree Size for Urban Streets

Street width	Sidewalk width	Building setback	Tree size
Narrow (Less than 4 m)	Less than 3 m	No turning back	-
		4 m or more	Average
Wide and avenue (More than 6 m)	More than 3 m	No recoil	Average
		4 m or more	Big

Adapted from Miranda, (1970)

Table 3. Land use and land cover classes in the urban area of Petrolina municipality in the years 1985, 1990, 2000, and 2019.

Use classe (Mapbiomas)	1985	1990	2000	2019
Forest formation	2,40	3,74	13,62	19,67
Savanna formation	1353,54	1294,79	981,26	733,97
Rural formation	1643,21	1485,29	1342,95	292,34
Pasture	668,09	1033,07	894,47	322,52
Sugar cane	-	2,14	-	-
Mosaic of agriculture and pasture	1861,93	1268,26	552,72	635,07
Urban infrastructure	1222,86	1768,11	3026,49	4761,39
Other non-vegetated areas	127,48	17,63	-	-
River	35,25	39,61	38,46	27,51
Perennial crops	-	0,80	63,83	57,60
Other temporary crops	-	1,34	0,98	64,72
Total	6914,78	6914,78	6914,78	6914,78

Source: Mapbiomas (2020)

Table 4. List and frequency of the main species inventoried in Petrolina-PE

Common name	Scientific name	Nº of trees	Total (%)	Accumulated (%)
Castanhola	<i>Terminalia catappa</i> L.	4428	49,89	49,89
Algaroba	<i>Prosopis juliflora</i> (SW) DC.	1152	12,98	62,87
Canafistula	<i>Cassia siamea</i> Lam.	734	8,27	71,14
Oiti	<i>Moquilia tomentosa</i> Benth.	519	5,85	76,99
Flamboyant	<i>Delonix regia</i> Raf.	448	5,05	82,04

Bisnagueira	<i>Spathodea campanulata</i> P. Beauv.	269	3,03	85,07
Mangueira	<i>Mangifera indica</i> L.	182	2,05	87,12
Azeitona	<i>Syzygium cumini</i> (L.) Skeels	128	1,44	88,56
Chapéu de Napoleão	<i>Thevestia peruviana</i> Schum.	88	0,99	89,55
Jambo	<i>Syzygium malaccense</i> (L.) Merr. & L. M. Perry.	87	0,98	90,53
Coqueiro	<i>Cocos nucifera</i> L.	73	0,83	91,96
Palmeira Imperial	<i>Roystonea regia</i> O. F. Cook	70	0,79	92,15
Sombreiro	<i>Clitoria fairchildiana</i> R.A.Howard	51	0,57	92,72
Chuva de Ouro	<i>Cassia fistula</i> L.	50	0,56	93,28
Espirradeira	<i>Nerium oleander</i> L.	50	0,56	93,84
Espinheiro	<i>Pithecelobium dulce</i> Benth	45	0,51	94,35
Munguba	<i>Pachira aquatica</i> Aubl	44	0,50	94,85
Other species	-	458	5,15	100,00
Total	71 species	8876	-	100,00

Adapted from Lima et al. (1990)

Table 5. Species, individuals, and index of number of trees/km of sidewalk according to neighborhoods.

Neighborhood	Nº of species	Trees (%)	Sidewalk (Km)	Sidewalk (Arv/Km)
João de Deus	13	240 (2,70)	25,22	9,52
Jardim São Paulo/Alto do Cocá	13	83 (0,94)	27,94	2,97
Massangano	20	253 (2,85)	57,38	4,41
Jardim Amazonas	19	398 (4,49)	54,50	7,30
Jardim Maravilha	26	509 (5,73)	36,20	14,06
Ouro Preto	13	148 (1,67)	26,04	5,68
Palhinhas/Atrás da Banca	31	485 (5,46)	30,91	15,69
Gersino Coelho	26	626 (7,05)	31,55	19,84
Km 2	25	626 (7,05)	16,90	37,04
Distrito Industrial	7	87 (0,98)	29,40	2,96
Centro	42	1754 (19,76)	53,50	32,79
Vila Mocó/Jardim Paulo Afonso	23	398 (4,49)	10,72	37,13
Caminho do Sol/Manoel do Arroz	15	222 (2,50)	26,32	8,43
José e Maria	33	733 (8,26)	46,92	15,62
Maria Auxiliadora	17	256 (2,88)	17,70	14,46
Alto Cheiroso/Colina Imperial	22	371 (4,18)	35,60	10,42
Ipsep/Loteamento Recife	12	101 (1,14)	43,06	2,34
Areia Branca	36	846 (9,53)	47,00	18,00
Vila Eduardo	24	715 (8,06)	40,40	17,70
Alto da Boa Vista/São Gonçalo	5	25 (0,28)	24,68	1,01
Total	71	8.876 (100)	678,42	-

Adapted from Lima et al. (1990)

Table 6. List of species, silvicultural parameters such as circumference at breast height (CBH), crown diameter (CD), height of the first bifurcation (HB), and observed conditions in public streets versus trees, including distance from curb (C), distance from construction (CD), distance from wiring (DW), spacing (SP), and free growth area of plants (FGA) in streets of Petrolina-PE.

Species	CBH (cm)	CD (cm)	HB (m)	C (m)	CD (m)	DW (m)	SP (m)	FGA (m)	
								Sidewalk	Central
<i>Terminalia catappa</i>	58,88	6,08	3,09	0,43	1,47	0,35	8,13	0,39	0,62
<i>Prosopis juliflora</i>	93,13	5,22	1,80	0,24	1,41	0,06	8,18	0,42	0,69
<i>Spatodea campanulata</i>	94,70	5,27	2,55	0,20	1,39	0,32	9,38	0,49	1,49
<i>Cassia siamea</i>	37,78	3,93	1,84	0,50	1,70	0,19	6,05	0,42	-
<i>Delonix regia</i>	71,79	5,34	1,85	0,65	1,25	0,42	9,23	0,81	*
<i>Moquilia tomentosa</i>	50,89	4,07	1,33	0,63	1,26	0,17	9,64	0,47	0,66
<i>Thevestia. peruviana</i>	13,00	2,43	1,12	-	-	-	5,84	-	*
<i>Cocus nucifera</i>	84,04	5,74	-	0,47	3,69	1,03	8,03	0,80	-
<i>Syzygium malaccense</i>	40,78	3,22	1,63	0,63	1,57	0,10	6,04	0,34	-
<i>Mangifera indica</i>	33,71	2,23	1,62	0,49	2,00	0,13	7,00	0,37	*
<i>Eucalyptus sp</i>	138,23	8,94	-	-	-	-	6,29	-	1,02

*Free area without sidewalk paving

Adapted from Lima et al. (1990)

Table 7. Percentage and number of individuals of native and exotic species in Petrolina's urban arborization in 2009.

Origin/specie	Number of individuals	Percentage (%)
Exotic	2824	90,22
Native	306	9,78
Total	3130	100,00

Adapted from Oliveira et al. (2009)

Tabela 8. Espécies e Famílias amostradas em seis bairros da cidade de Patos-PB e sua origem, no período de 19/09/2015 a 23/10/2016. bairros: 1) Brasília; 2) Maternidade; 3) Novo Horizonte; 4) Liberdade; 5) Centro; 6) Jatobá.

Families/Species	Common Name	Origin	Registration Number	Neighborhood
ANACARDIACEAE				
<i>Anacardium occidentale</i> L.	Cajueiro	Exotic	7165	2
<i>Mangifera indica</i> L.	Mangueira	Exotic	7180	1,2,3,4,6
<i>Astronium urundeuva</i> (M.Allemão) Engl.	Aroeira	Native	7182	4
<i>Spondias dulcis</i> Parkinson	Cajarana	Exotic	7191	2
<i>Nerium oleander</i> L.	Espirradeira	Exotic	7183	5
APOCYNACEAE				
<i>Plumeria pudica</i> Jacq.	Jasmim-do-Caribe	Exotic	7187	1,2,3,6
<i>Thevetia peruviana</i> (Pers.) K.Schum	Chapéu de Napoleão	Native	7194	4
ARECACEAE				

<i>Roystonea regia</i> (Kunth) O. F. Cook	Palmeira-real	Exotic	7189	1
<i>Dyopsis decaryi</i> (Jum.) Beentje & J. Dransf.	Palmeira-triangular	Exotic	7172	5
<i>Dyopsis lutescens</i> (H.Wendl.) Beentje & J.Dransf.	Palmeira-areca	Exotic	7173	1,2
<i>Phoenix roebelenii</i> O'Brien	Tamareira-de-Jardim	Exotic	7193	2
<i>Veitchia merrillii</i> (Becc.) H.E.Moore	Palmeira-de-manila	Exotic	7198	1,2,5
BIGNONIACEAE				
<i>Handroanthus chrysotrichus</i> (Mart. ex DC.) Mattos	Ipê-amarelo	Native	7177	5
<i>Handroanthus impetiginosus</i> (Mart. ex DC.)	Ipê-roxo	Native	7178	1,2,3,4,5
<i>Tabebuia aurea</i> (Silva Manso) Benth. & Hook. f. ex S.Moore	Craibeira	Native	7194	2,3,4,5
<i>Tecoma stans</i> (L.) Juss. ex Kun	Ipê-mirim	Exotic	7195	1,6
BORAGINACEAE				
<i>Cordia africana</i> Lam.	Cola	Exotic	7170	1,2,3,4,5,6
COMBRETACEAE				
<i>Terminalia catappa</i> L.	Castanhola	Exotic	7196	1,2,3,5,6
EUPHORBIACEAE				
<i>Cnidoscolus quercifolius</i> Pohl.	Favela	Native	7169	4
<i>Jatropha mollissima</i> (Pohl) Baill.	Pinhão-bravo	Native	7179	2
FABACEAE				
<i>Adenanthera pavonina</i> L.	Falso-pau-Brasil	Exotic	7162	1,2,4,5,6
<i>Albizia lebbek</i> L. (Benth)	Esponjinha	Exotic	7163	1,2,4,5,6
<i>Bauhinia monandra</i> Kurz	Pata-de-vaca	Exotic	7166	6
<i>Cassia fistula</i> L.	Chuva-de-ouro	Exotic	7167	5,6
<i>Delonix regia</i> (Bojer ex Hook.) Raf.	Flaboyant	Exotic	7171	2,3,4,5
<i>Erythrina velutina</i> Willd	Mulungu	Native	7174	4
<i>Pithecellobium dulce</i> (Roxb.) Benth.	Mata-Fome	Exotic	7186	1,2,4,5,6
<i>Prosopis juliflora</i> (Sw.) DC.	Algaroba	Exotic	7188	1,2,3,4,5,6
<i>Senna siamea</i> (Lam.) H.S.Irwin & Barneby	Cássia	Exotic	7190	1,2,3,4,5,6
<i>Tamarindus indica</i> L.	Tamarineira	Exotic	7185	6
MALVACEAE				
<i>Pachira aquatica</i> Aubl.	Munguba	Native		1
MELIACEAE				
<i>Azadirachta indica</i> A. Juss.	Nim	Exotic	7164	1,2,3,4,5,6
MORACEAE				
<i>Ficus benjamina</i> L.	Ficus-benjamim	Exotic	7176	1,2,3,4,5,6
MORINGACEAE				
<i>Moringa oleifera</i> Lam.	Moringa	Exotic	7181	4
MYRTACEAE				
<i>Eucalyptus globulus</i> Labill	Eucalipto	Exotic	7175	2
<i>Syzygium cumini</i> (L.) Skeels	Azeitona	Exotic	7192	2
RHAMNACEAE				
<i>Sarcophalus joazeiro</i> Mart.	Joazeiro	Native	7197	6
RUTACEAE				
<i>Citrus limonum</i> Risso	Limão	Exotic	7168	4

Source: Borges, (2019)

Figure 1. Vegetation cover and land use in the urban area of Petrolina municipality, in the years 1985, 1990, 2000 e 2019.

Source: Prepared at the Geoprocessing Laboratory of Embrapa Semiárido

Figure 2. Local native species used in urban arborization of Petrolina-PE:

A) Angico – *Anadenanthera colubrina*, B) Catingueira verdadeira – *Cenostigma pyramidale* (Tul.) Gagnon & G.P.Lewis, C) Licuri – *Syagrus coronata*, D) Craibeira – *Tabebuia aurea* in two phenophases, E) Joazeiro – *Sarcomphalus joazeiro*, Umbuzeiro – *Spondias tuberosa*, Pau d’arco – *Handroanthus impetiginosus*.

Photos: Marcos Antônio Drumond

Figure 3. Native species from other Brazilian biomes used in urban arborization of Petrolina-PE: A) Pau-Brasil – *Paubrasilia echinata*, B) Oiti - *Moquilea tomentosa*, C) Sibipiruna – *Cenostigma pluviosum*, D) Paineira – *Ceiba speciosa*, E) Pau-d’arco – *Handroanthus impetiginosus*, F) – Canafistula - *Senna spectabilis*.

Photos: Marcos Antônio Drumond

Figure 4. Exotic species used in urban arborization of Petrolina-PE: A), Ficus - *Ficus benjamim*, B) Mangueira - *Mangifera indica*, C) Algarobeira - *Prosopis juliflora*, D), Palmeira-veitchia - *Veitchia merrillii*, E) Mata-fome - *Pithecellobium dulce*, F) Nim - *Azadiractha indica*, G) Moringa - *Moringa oleifera*, H) Tamareira *Phoenix dactylifera* e I) Cola - *Cordia africana*.

Photos: Marcos Antônio Drumond

Figure 5. A) *Delonix regia*; B) *Senna siamea*; C) *Cassia fistula*; D) *Bauhinia monandra*; E) *Tamarindus indica*; F) *Albizia lebekk*; G) *Erythrina velutina*; H) *Adenanthera pavonina*; I) *Prosopis juliflora*; J) *Pithecellobium dulce*

Photos: Danniely A. B. Borges

Figure 6. A) *Veitchia merrillii*; B) *Dypsis decaryi*; C) *Phoenix roebelenii* O'Brien; D) *Roystonea regia*; E) *Dypsis lutescens*

Photos: Danniely A. B. Borges

Figure 7. A) *Cordia africana*; B) *Terminalia catappa*; C) *Cnidocolus quercifolius*; D) *Jatropha mollissima*; E) *Pachira aquatica*; F) *Azadirachta indica*

Photos: Danniely A. B. Borges

Figure 8. A) *Moringa oleifera*; B) *Ficus benjamina*; C) *Eucalyptus globulus*; D) *Syzygium cumini*; E) *Sarcomphalus joazeiro*; F) *Citrus limonum*

Photos: Danniely A. B. Borges

Cite this Article: Marcos Antônio Drumond, Visêldo Ribeiro de Oliveira, Danniely Alves Benício Borges, Iêdo Bezerra Sá, Maria do Carmo Learth Cunha (2025). Urban arborization in cities of the Brazilian Semiarid: Retrospective analysis and future perspectives. *International Journal of Current Science Research and Review*, 8(12), pp. 6383-6400. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.47191/ijcsrr/V8-i12-50>